

TEACHING WRITING USING INTERNET TECHNOLOGIES IN SCHOOLS.

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Abstract: The article is aimed at exploring the teaching writing using information technologies at schools.

More precisely, it studies the effects of using some techniques of teaching writing using internet technologies at schools. It is mainly devoted to illustrate the ways of enhancing writing skills and tactics. There are lots of writing activities obtainable within the ESL galaxy for you to pick out from and adapt in case you wish. In all likelihood thousands, however preserving your students in thoughts when selecting one is quite likely the maximum critical thing. ESL writing should be fun and encouraging, although a lot of us can remember the boring essays we had to scribble out in faculty. So wreck the mildew and positioned a dash of pleasure into your writing lesson. Earlier than letting your keen students discover the fun of writing, it's miles essential that they have the right expertise to do so. Commonly, ESL writing activities could be done inside the production stage of your presentation, practice and manufacturing lesson plan. You will have some short writing activities inside the exercise level, but those are specially to set your students up with the competencies they want to really display off their stuff inside the manufacturing stage. Production is where students are left more to their own gadgets—they will finally get a risk to attempt their hand at full-on english writing. A good coaching tactic to make certain your students are ready to move into the manufacturing activity is to test in with them on occasion. Ask questions that

revolve around the brand new writing fabric, questions which can best be answerable in the event that they really recognise what is going on. Your exercise writing activities also are excellent for this. Probabilities are, if students are having hassle with the practice activities, you may want to preserve off on the manufacturing exercises for a chunk longer. Whilst everybody is ready, assured and ready to begin writing with little steerage, you may than introduce the pro-motion writing interest. Recall, that is your students' time to polish, so provide them all the information they want to be successful (Yong Mei, 2010). Providing clear and concise instructions on ESL writing activities is very important. You can view the structure needed to complete the task by handing out handouts or writing outline instructions on the board. Structural analysis is very important and will lead to less frustration, as your students will begin to create their amazing writing work. After all key aspects of the activity are completed, with a short question and answer to the question of what is expected, release them. It is your time to wander around the room and feel good while watching your students do this using the methods and information that you presented earlier. Be available for any questions or problems that may arise, you will be their editor and reflect in many ways throughout the activity.

1. Start small with tweets

Twitter, Tweeting and Tweets have become part of major social networks. These small pieces of information revolutionized human experience by sharing thoughts that would otherwise be just thoughts. Tweets can be an effective tool in writing ESL for many reasons. Although on Twitter during the lesson, there is a different condemnation when you present new material for your class, you can use this phenomenon on social networks for teaching. Your students are likely familiar with tweets. This means that they can immediately relate to the topics and tasks that you assign to them. Depending on the age and interests of your students, you can even create a real board for tweets in the classroom, where you will type short texts from students. You can also open your Twitter profile in the classroom,

allowing your students to post their new English tweets to the world. Tweets are great for small beginners, limiting your students to 140 characters or less. This means that they will need to focus their writing on one specific topic. The structure of tweets is almost non-existent, so your students can become more creative. Students will understand activities without any rigorous structural or stylistic information. In addition, tweets allow students to explore simpler topics and fun topics. A tweet can discuss films, television shows, and other topics in popular culture. A great example of an ESL Twitter activity is using something related to their daily lives. Let's say all your students are delighted with the upcoming movie. You will present the trailer of the film, and let them watch it, discuss and ask any questions that may arise. This is great for some communicative practice. After they discuss the film, give them handouts with three empty spaces for tweets. Each tweet place will have its own theme. Remind them that they have 140 characters to create a short message about the theme of the film. For example, one subject may be about the main actor, so your students will tweet about the actor, his appearance, his attitude or what he may have done in the movie trailer. After they have successfully written their tweets, you can discuss them, transfer some of the communication lessons to the lesson and, if appropriate, start tweeting to the world using a cool Twitter account. Your students will be more than happy to see their words on the Internet for everyone to read. This is a great confidence in their writing!

2. Write Informative, Useful Emails

Emails have become the foundation of our world. They are fundamental in our and expert life. Very few people today send genuine letters composed or anything else. Emails are the main source of correspondence between people around the world. That is why composing e-mail is the key to successful correspondence. This ESL composer movement is more intended for young adult and adult students, since in principle young people do not send so many messages. Emails can be a troubling task for your students, especially in a different, strange language that they are not yet sure about. You can use the email compilation action

to enable your students to build confidence and gradually gain good writing skills in English. Similarly, there are other annoying message components for your understudies, such as legal language, structure, and layout. Organizing email can be as time-consuming as compiling it, so investing in energy research and exploring the elements of email structure is fundamental. When your understudies are well-structured, familiarize them with certain components of formal and random writing. Using certain words may be the most ideal approach for moving on to formal and casual messages, but do not overload your students with something excessive. Recall that the focus of the exercise is on genuine composition, rather than talking about wit. This is all that someone might need to start with the “Sir” and “Madam” nuts for official presentations, as well as “Sincerely” or “Best Regards” when packing the letter. With structure and formal / random fundamentals, you can get a drawing up of your deputies. One incredible email composing action can be fat with composing and informative abilities. Connect your understudies and give them a diagram for a specific email subject. Suppose that attention is paid to the upcoming companion's birthday celebration. This will cause random email trading between two people. Students A will be provided with one worksheet explaining the intricacies of a birthday party for a companion. They will have to write an email to their accomplice, in which he welcomes and explains the key parts of the meeting. Student B will examine the email greeting and create a response based on the data that he has without any other table. This worksheet should contain information about circumstances for Student B. Perhaps Student B may not be able to attend the meeting until some other time, or they may need to get some information about the nutritious meal or blessings. At this time, you can go around the room and make sure that everyone is concentrated around the main work. Answer any questions that may arise while driving.

3. Make Creative Advertisements

Promotions cover us every day, and you can probably bet that your understudies will receive some of their favorite advertisements. This action can be

for all ages and can be adapted to most learners and their needs. Notifications are an extraordinary method to tell your students how best to compose with a flare. They will appreciate the study of the subject and the use of amazing ingenuity, which they suppressed in them after the introductory and practical stages. This incredible ESL composer movement can allow your students to use their descriptive words even more unconditionally. Understanding when and how to put descriptive words into their composition is a great experience. Using promotions as part of an exercise has a huge amount of benefits for both you and you. The best part of an advertising creation exercise is that you will never lack phenomenal and instructive guides to show your understudies. There are countless advertisements on the planet. You can find any view or point that you need only with a click of the mouse or by turning the page of the log. Models are important when you talk about the structure of your backups and how to better plan your unique advertising, so use each of these incredible models. Creating ads, in addition, is an incredible method for implementing informative abilities by mixing or collecting your understudies. Your understudies can build their thoughts by comprehending with their colleagues, truly pushing out these inventive thoughts and attracting descriptive words. An extraordinary promotion action is to keep your students focused on the subject you are bringing to class. Let them see him, get in touch with him, use him, etc. The presence of material participation in the subject for which they will make up is fundamental, as a rule. Students will probably not want to talk in detail about what they can just find in the image, so give them the opportunity to experience it.

4. The structure of informative reports

Another incredible ESL compilation step to include in your exercise book is reporting. Sooner or later in the life of each understudy they will need to compile a report, and many have just done it in their own language. Reporting is a fundamental part of the life of the scientific community and business, so you can expand the structure with which they may be familiar. Reporting can improve your alternate professions and even increase their ESL scores. The compilation of the

report additionally contains an information component. Less during the composer movement, however later, which allows your students to present their reports before class and field inquiries regarding background material. This is another manufacturer of abilities, which, in your opinion, does not approve of training, since many of them can work in universal organizations, and that is why they decided to study English with you. Displaying their report is also a great way to gain the trust of your understudies both in correspondence and in composition. They will have the opportunity to understand what works and what doesn't, after a couple of exercises and intros that make up the report. Extending these capabilities is the foundation of ESL. From many points of view, reporting is not as serious as other activities. Your understudies will not write a lot of two to two. The requirement to activate visual effects is not so fundamental. Reporting is increasingly about research and the structure that makes up it. Demonstration of their legal structure is of great importance. You can strengthen the reporting structure that you demonstrated, and they rehearsed by handing out a worksheet outlining the legal structure of the report. You might even have this on the board for their REFERENCES. In fact, you just let them draw up their report using the material provided, but with a slight curve. Give them a question or problem to study in their report. If you and your understudies did not have the opportunity to talk about bears that have recently eaten fish in Yellowstone Park, tell them about it and tell about them. For example, you may ask them: "Consider the possibility that the fish were no longer there. This direct investigation and distortion of the topic will cause a creative explosion of the mind. This is impeccable with respect to reporting, and now they must really think and place their instructive thoughts in the correct structure of the report. They should be solid subject sentences with extraordinary auxiliary sentences that bring everything together. Keep your understudies in good shape when writing reports, and you will have students eager to write more reports (Bromely, 2005).

5. Craft a Class Newsletter/Newspaper

This ESL writing job is a bit more intense and will allow your students to take advantage of various aspects of their ESL knowledge. Creating a classy newsletter will help you develop the skills of teamwork, communication, listening, speaking and, of course, writing. This can be a long, constantly changing ESL letter, which will be interesting and interesting for your students. Sharing information about their class with the world will make them excited for the next writing lesson. There are many layers of class involvement involved in this. Communication skills will be crucial when creating a classroom newspaper or newsletter, as students will begin to brainstorm what content to include. You can break up your students into paired writing groups or leave them in a freer position, no matter what you choose. It is simply important to remember that participation in a group is essential for the success of this activity. You and your students should participate in a detailed brainstorming session on which topics to choose, how to format the newsletter, and so on. This is a great way to get everyone involved and get involved in writing articles, removing the frightening aspects that prevent ESL from being written in the classroom. In addition, they can share their pride in the successes of their class in English. First of all, you have to decide whether you want couples or individual authors for each topic. It often depends on you and the size of the class. Suppose you have a large class, and you have divided the students into pairs. Each pair will be given a topic for this week's newsletter, and you will explain the details related to their topic during the presentation, going through each couple's topic together as a class. After all, this is a cool newsletter. Once the couple has decided on their topic, you will give each of them specific handouts regarding their topic at the practice stage to begin a creative brainstorming session with their partner. First, the topics ought to be general: food, travel, news, fashion, technology and so on. This ensures that each student is focused on one topic. Each week, topics can alter from one pair to another, giving your students the experience of writing different topics. After your passionate couples have written their drafts at the practice stage, you can transfer them to production and let them become a co-author of their article for

publication in the newsletter. Once all the articles are ready, you can view them together with the class, and everyone will be able to discuss and get better communication practice by putting together the weekly newsletter. It can be concluded that online materials for teaching writing influence the best writing result for school students than materials taken from a textbook.

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